

Art of Delay: Procrastination in Relation with the Hybrid Work Environment and Task Performance

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Abstract:- One of the frequent behaviors of employees in organization is procrastination, and when it gets more pragmatic and the employee's perception and actions shift to be more distinctive and unmotivated, it will ruin the organization's motivation and effective growth. The most common causes of procrastination are hybrid work environment, which causes individuals become apathetic about taking serious action when a problem occurs. Most of government and private organization are trying to give speed to their working process and it will cause a big mismanagement of the employee's roles which cause lots of improper division of the roles and bring role conflict among employees. Therefore, remote job which leads to repetition procrastination actions and in-office work related stress increase procrastination behavior in employees. The current study uses a systematic literature review to learn about the link between procrastination, employee procrastination, and compare task performance in two type of work environment, and it will pave the way for future research into the direct influence of procrastination and performance of remote job workers and in office workers. To define the exact meaning of procrastination and to understand the importance of and the negative effects of procrastination, as well as to identify mismanagement of roles within the organization, it is necessary to conduct a research paper based on previous literature to find ways to reduce procrastination in organizations.

Keywords:- Hybrid Work Environment, Procrastination, Task Performance, Team Procrastination Behavior, Work-Related Stress.

I. INTRODUCTION

Procrastination seems to be a big concern. Scholars most studily illustrate it as being not good, destructive, and silly. Mitigating this view, various revisions have related it to distinct presentation, with the procrastinating action more poorly overall, and to person well-being, with the procrastination being more wretched in the long duration. At larger levels of investigation, procrastination has been related to numerous managerial and social problems (Steel, 2010).

Procrastination is the deliberate postponement of choices or actions. For example, a person is procrastinating when they put off working on a task until the last minute, even if they know it would be better if they started earlier. Procrastination is a widespread issue that can lead to a variety of problems, including missed opportunities and increased stress. Furthermore, individuals frequently miscalculate it, making it difficult to quit delaying (Singh et al., 2018). Procrastination is a frequent problem that affects around 20% of individuals, including attorneys, corporate leaders, and college professors. Furthermore, procrastination is especially widespread among some demographics, such as college students, with around half of them procrastinating chronically (Singh, 2017). Few studies have been undertaken in other organisations; research on procrastination has mostly been done in the educational sector. Procrastination has more than one definition. It is not only limited to delay; the delay itself must be unreasonable. (Steel, 2010).

A work setting that incorporates both in-person and remote work arrangements is referred to as a "hybrid workplace". Employees may divide their time between working in the office and working remotely from a location like their home or another suitable location thanks to the flexible model. Due in large part to the COVID-19 epidemic, which hastened the adoption of remote work practices, this idea has received a great deal of attention and acceptance (Morikawa, 2021). The hybrid workplace concept understands that there are a variety of work options and situations. With the potential to increase job happiness, productivity, and employee retention, it attempts to strike a balance between the advantages of in-person involvement and the flexibility of remote work (Singh and Bala, 2021).

➤ Procrastination

According to Klingsieck (2013), procrastination is a condition of being in favour of tomorrow. Unless it becomes illogical, procrastination refers to more than merely delaying (Steel, 2010). To accomplish goals, a leader must make timely strategic and tactical judgements. Any choice that is made too late is useless and leads in lost opportunities for financial gain. Additionally, effective decision-making by the leader propels the organisation to its highest level of achievement. Procrastination happens despite the need of making decisions quickly in organisations (Singh et al., 2021).

We are all distinctive in our own ways. Our experiences, circumstances, attitudes, aptitudes, and ideals appear to be somewhat similar, yet our responses differ. In a company, employees respond to every circumstance in a distinctive way. They must make modifications at every stage of their lives as a result of both personal and environmental factors (Singh and Bala, 2020).

The practise of delaying or postponing crucial duties in favour of less important or more pleasurable pursuits is known as procrastination. Procrastination comes in a variety of forms, each having its own underlying causes and traits (Singh et al., 2022). The many forms of procrastination are described here. Classic Procrastination: This is the form of procrastination that occurs when people put off chores without a good cause. They could have a propensity to overestimate how long a task will take to do, giving them the impression that they have more time than they actually have.

Perfectionist Procrastination: Because of their extremely high expectations, perfectionists frequently struggle with procrastination. Because of this, people put off starting or finishing chores to avoid feeling inadequate or failing (Singh et al., 2015). Another synonym for procrastination is the fear of failure or success, since people delay tasks out of a fear of either one. They may put off working on projects because they are concerned that their efforts won't be sufficient (Singh et al., 2021).

Putting off tasks that entail making decisions is known as decisional procrastination. People may put off taking action out of uncertainty regarding the appropriate course of action or fear of making the incorrect decision (Banger et al., 2017).

External diversions: People who are tempted away from their job by external diversions like alerts, social media, and other entertainment may procrastinate (Singh et al., 2015).

➤ *Hybrid Work Environment*

'Hybrid' is not a very unique word. Over the years, it has been used in a variety of representations. In more recent times, the term "hybrid" has come to signify a whole new aspect of how technology has influenced how people live their lives. We are familiar with the manner of life in our own country, to be sure. The blended system is another name for a hybrid system. It often happens when there is a need to fairly balance two different types of requests in order to prevent any clashes or conflicts. The hybrid system is a project that was started to address the particular requirements of a system's or organization's active parties. For jobs that historically needed human connection and communication, modern technologies are making it simpler to locate alternatives to human resources (Singh et al., 2023). A hybrid arrangement should provide a solution to the problems of location, distance, cost, availability, and management if it is present in a setting with specific criteria. Hybridity is unquestionably a result of technological development. It combines the physical work

arrangement and the remote work system to describe hybridity, particularly in a workplace (Cook et al., 2020). In essence, some people work physically on the premises of the company or organisation, while others operate virtually thanks to the internet. This arrangement may also apply to the same group of individuals, in which case they would be permitted to work part of each week on-site at the business and the rest of the time remotely (Cook et al., 2020).

All facets of life have been impacted by COVID-19 (Harris & Moss, 2020). Every country suffered from this pandemic, which was unique from past outbreaks. Numerous preventative actions were attempted by governments all around the world to limit the disease's spread. The governments of numerous nations imposed a severe lockdown and incarceration. Governments all across the world implemented the required precautions to stop the spread of COVID-19 at that point, and the work-from-home or remote work approach was introduced (Singh et al., 2023).

➤ *Task Performance*

Performance is a broad concept. Numerous psychological and non-psychological elements are connected to it. Performance is described as "the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed" by Business Dictionary (2016). Performance in a contract is defined as the completion of an obligation in a way that absolves the performer of all obligations under the contract. The performance is influenced by a number of psychological and non-psychological factors (Singh, 2023). Performance is only a ratio between input behaviour and manufacturing output. It is an intricate area of behaviour science. The collective performance of an organization's employees determines its performance. As a result, social scientists and administration experts are paying closer attention to execution as a result of the altering state of the global economies. It is obvious that several facets of human behaviour, such as personality, drive, leadership, procrastination, attitude, etc., have an impact on output (Singh, 2019).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Ariely & Steel et al. 2001) had shown the procrastination's considerable effect on performance. (Wertenbroch et al., 2002) looked at that deadline; they found that it did not improve task performance while controlling procrastinating behaviour. Poor working conditions have been investigated as having an impact on employee performance (Chandrasekar, 2011). (Singh et al., 2017) studied the procrastination tendencies of instructors in several disciplines. The current study adjusts the association between demographic characteristics and procrastination, finding a strong influence of respondents' profiles on their procrastinating habit. Additionally, a strong correlation between respondents' procrastinating habit and age was discovered (Singh, 2017) looked at how procrastination affects

hotel managers' psychological performance. According to Baumeister & Scher (1988), procrastination has a detrimental impact on performance. (Singh, 2022) Being environmentally conscious is crucial for producing better job results. By examining the mediating roles of environmental sensitivity (ES) and environmental attitude (EA) on the link between environmental knowledge (EK) and environmental behavioural intention (EBI), this study aims to close a research gap. Cano Kollmann et al. (2018) claim that due to the rapid advancements in digitization in the HR business, non-technical personnel may not only lose their jobs but also become "unemployable" and have their positions off shored, completely eliminated, or become less value. According to John and Mannix (2001), effective team communication can lessen the detrimental consequences of interpersonal conflict on the effectiveness of the group.

III. CONCLUSION

It is logically argued that procrastination is the art of delay, and many employees procrastinate intentionally, and some try to delay their work to take control over their work-job conflict, due to which they always avoid working hard and showing decent work performance. According to the above literature, some scholars pointed out that numerous terms are involved in procrastination behaviour, whether this affects employee performance or whether the work environment is suitable for procrastinating verall. To summarize, i it is about the work environment, which can significantly define this: if the work environment and work tasks are not interesting and employees feel demotivated, they look for alternative ways to procrastinate, and in the term hybrid work environment, it means that organisations give the employee some chance and leave the employee to attempt procrastination. Finally, procrastination greatly affects employee task performance, and if it continues and employees take advantage of this, this will cause mismanagement problems in the organisation, whereas good leadership and stewardship increase employee ownership and produce good work from the employees.

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